

PEDAGOGICAL BASES FOR PROVIDING ACADEMIC MOBILITY OF STUDENTS

Dustnazar Omonovich Khimmataliyev

Professor of Chirchik state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773052>

Abstract. *Today there is a steady demand for specialists who are competent, competitive, versatile, able to work effectively at the level of world standards in their specialty, capable of continuous professional growth. Today requires the training of students of educational institutions within the country on the basis of contracts, memorandums and other agreements for an agreed period, the organization of the educational process for the exchange of students of higher educational institutions in the field of knowledge.*

The article highlights the pedagogical principles of ensuring the academic mobility of students, the issues of training personnel ready for mobility.

Keywords: *program, organization, project, partnership, lecture, seminar, group, internship, research.*

Introduction

Comprehensive globalization and integration as the main trends of the modern world development have opened up new aspects for the higher education system. Academic mobility, which is a guarantee of the quality of education in higher education institutions, contributes to the qualitative improvement of academic cooperation and the formation of competent personnel, occupies a worthy place in the international labor market. Therefore, the problem of pedagogical support of academic mobility of students is in the center of special attention of scientists, the international community, employers, the state and students.

According to the Presidential Decree №PD-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2021 "On additional measures to ensure the academic and organizational-management independence of state higher education institutions", from the 2022/2023 academic year financial independence was granted to state higher education institutions in the field of academic independence : approval of educational plans, educational programs, qualification requirements on the basis of professional standards, determining the form of education taking into account the language of education and the characteristics of educational directions and specialties; determining duration of studies for undergraduate education and master's specialties; determining the cost of studying in doctoral studies on the basis of a fee-contract, admission to doctoral studies based on selection in addition to the quota by allocating grants from extra-budgetary funds; approval of the procedure for scientific supervision of doctoral students and independent researchers; introduction of part-time, distance and evening forms of education at the master's level, introduction of a system of providing double qualifications, including practical qualifications, in educational areas and specialties; on the basis of mutual agreements, additional powers such as the implementation of academic mobility with higher education institutions are given.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Today, the training of competent, competitive, well-rounded personnel capable of working efficiently at the level of world standards in their specialty, ready for continuous professional growth and mobility of specialists is a factor in solving the tasks set by the labor market.

In recent years, a number of theses have been defended on the problems of developing academic mobility in the field of pedagogy. In particular, J.V. Znovenko, development of academic mobility of students of pedagogical university in the conditions of continuous education (J.V. Znovenko, Omsk, 2008); A.N. Sheremet, formation of academic mobility of future informatics teachers using information and communication technologies (A.N. Sheremet, Novokuznetsk, 2009), A.V. Kuzmin, problems of managing academic mobility as a factor in the development of international integration in education (A.V. Kuzmin, Saint-Petersburg, 2007) and studied the methods of evaluating the effectiveness of the innovative educational program and the level of education.

Methodology of research

In fact, academic mobility, moving from one area to another for education, is a process with a very long history. People went to study from the village to the city, from the city to the capital, from the capital to the countries with developed education and economy.

Academic mobility means a system of training students of educational institutions within a certain country for an agreed period of time based on contracts, memorandums and other agreements. For example, 2 higher education institutions, whose fields of knowledge are mutually compatible, organize an educational process by exchanging students for a certain period of time.

Within the implementation of the Bologna process in Europe, the provision of academic mobility, which is one of the important elements contributing to the entry of higher education institutions into the international arena, has been actively developed.

Academic mobility is one of the important factors for achieving high performance in the higher education system. It serves to increase the quality of higher education through the possibility of comparing educational institutions with each other, mastering and introducing their important aspects. Mobility creates a basis for improving the structures of higher education institutions, state education standards, curricula.

Its participants can be students, academic and administrative staff of higher education institutions. In fact, international mobility provides an opportunity for professional adaptation and continuing education in the global labor market. Internal academic mobility provides convenience to students and their parents. In this case, the student submits information about having studied for a certain period of time to his main study, having mastered the relevant subjects and accumulating credits, he can continue his studies at the main educational institution.

Results of research

Academic mobility primarily helps to develop the following global tasks:

- improving the quality of higher education;
- establishing relations with educational organizations in other countries;
- increasing the reputation of scientific and pedagogical activities in the country;
- development of personal qualities of educational staff, such as communication skills or overcoming language barriers.

Promoting mobility for all participants in the Bologna Process is both a goal and a means. This process means the possibility of full participation and competitiveness in the formation of the common European space.

Staying in the field of international science and education requires a certain experience, and accordingly, unfortunately, today's educational institutions face a number of problems, such as:

- financing;
- language skills;
- lack of international academic mobility programs for teachers and researchers;
- that the target audience is not sufficiently informed about the new programs.

To solve them, it is necessary to create organizations that contribute to information about international projects and help in participation in international programs. Such educational organizations develop and improve the efficiency of international relations, receive information about international educational programs and international projects, introduce exchange programs, promote new ideas, attract participants, create new forms of cooperation, participate in lectures, seminars, group and individual consultations, independent. It is organized to carry out work, projects, exchange of teachers, internships and scientific research.

Mobile students are mainly divided into 2 groups:

free movers - students of this type go to other regions for education on their own initiative and desire;

students within the program - in which the higher education institution itself or one of its faculties implements exchange programs for students in agreement with another higher education institution. Programs can be both national and international. For example, the Erasmus program is one of the popular programs that allow student exchange.

The following can be noted as pedagogical bases for ensuring academic mobility of students:

1. Academic mobility of students shows the need and importance of applying the ideas of person-oriented, design-process approaches in education.
2. The effectiveness of the process of interaction between the teacher and students, the level of optimality, the need to create developed pedagogical conditions and pedagogical training correspond to the main rules of ensuring the academic mobility of students.
3. Pedagogical support of students' readiness for academic mobility shows an increase in educational efficiency.

Conclusions and suggestions

Ensuring the academic mobility of students in individual educational institutions and the higher education system on a global scale increases the level of integration of the educational institution into the European higher education area, develops a social direction in the field of higher education. This is an additional rating indicator of the effectiveness of educational activities for certain educational institutions.

"Academic mobile" students acquire personal qualities, theoretical knowledge, and relevant competences that allow them to participate in it. Pedagogical foundations of ensuring academic mobility of students:

- actualization of the need to form students' readiness for academic mobility as a quality of professional importance;

- readiness of the teacher for the role of teacher-consultant and the use of multimedia technologies at all stages of the web project;
- involvement and responsibility of students in studying;
- attracting "former" mobile students and students participating in academic mobility;
- active analysis of various academic mobility programs;
- consists of the variability of forming small study groups to complete the tasks of the webquest project, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On additional measures to ensure academic and organizational-management independence of state higher education institutions. No. PD-60. 24.12.2021.
2. Зновенко Ж.В. Развитие академической мобильности студентов педагогического вуза в условиях непрерывного образования : автореф. дис. . канд. пед. наук : 13.00.08 / Ж. В. Зновенко ; Омск. гос. пед. ун-т. Омск, 2008. -23 с
3. Шеремет А.Н. Формирование академической мобильности будущих учителей информатики средствами информационных и коммуникационных технологий : автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук : 13.00.08. - М, 2009.
4. Кузьмин А.В. Управление академической мобильностью как фактор развития международной интеграции в образовании : автореф. дис. . канд. экон. наук : 08.00.05 / А. В. Кузьмин ; Рос. гос. пед. ун-т им. А.И. Герцена. -Спб., 2007.-26 с.
5. Nurmamatov S., Davronov A. PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PROFILING METHODS IN PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. В8. – С. 1224-1227.
6. Mukhamedov, G. I., Usarov, J. E., Khimmataliev, D. O., Petrovna, C. V., Umirzakovich, T. K., & Khamidovna, G. S. (2023). General Classifications of Pedagogy and Psychology. *Telematique*, 22(01), 341-347.
7. Omonovich, K. D., & Mirzaahmadovna, M. S. (2023). The Relevance of the Dual Learning Model for Our Country. *Telematique*, 22(01), 265-274.
8. Omonovich X. D., Murodiljonovna G. U. THE ATTITUDE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS TOWARDS READING //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 266-270.